

"PROMOTING THE WORKS OF OYBEK AMONG THE YOUTH"

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Annotatsiya: Har bir millatning o'z tili, o'z dini, milliy qadriyatlari, millatni xalq darajasiga yetkaza olgan buyuk shaxslari, allomayu zamonlari bo'ladi. Ular tufayli milliylik, ona til, buyuk tarix, buyuk adabiyot va san'at asrlar osha sayqal topadi va rivojlanib boraveradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Adib, porloq ijod, yetuk rahbar, notiq, Qutluq' qon.

Аннотация: У каждого народа есть свой язык, своя религия, национальные ценности, великие личности, сумевшие вывести нацию на уровень нации и своей эпохи. Благодаря им национальность, родной язык, великая история, великая литература и искусство будут шлифоваться и развиваться веками.

Ключевые слова: Писатель, блестящий труд, опытный лидер, оратор, кровь Кутлука.

Annotation: Every nation has its own language, its own religion, national values, great personalities, scholars, and eras that have brought the nation to the level of a people. Thanks to them, nationality, native language, great history, great literature, and art have been refined and developed over the centuries.

One of the most prominent figures of the 20th century, a rare gem of Uzbek literature, a great writer, poet, scholar, and public figure, People's Writer of Uzbekistan, Muso Toshmuhammad oqli Oybek, is an extraordinary personality. Many scholars, intellectuals, and young researchers have been conducting studies and research for years on the remarkable life journey and brilliant works of this man. They have also published scientific and analytical articles in the media, including prestigious newspapers and journals. However, as young people, I believe it is essential for us to focus our attention on the works of this author that exemplify patience, contentment, sharp intellect, courage, humility, and a life led with love and loyalty. Not only should we read these works thoroughly, but we must also promote them to our peers.

In today's world, where rapid development is taking place and we are living in the global internet era, we must consciously understand both the positive and negative aspects of this environment. Only then can we return to books and become the kind, hospitable people that the world has long admired. We will be able to respect elders and honor the young, and these qualities can be nurtured through the study of books.

While life may physically prepare a person for many things, books are the ones that shape a person's character, manners, and morality, making them the truest and closest friend. It is important to bear this in mind. Furthermore, individuals who read extensively can become visionary leaders and eloquent speakers, and this power comes directly from books.

It is not without reason that we speak of the great writer and poet Muso Toshmuhammad oqli Oybek. His exemplary life journey, marked by overcoming numerous

challenges, his strong will in the face of adversity, and his beloved works have made him a cherished author among readers to this day.

I believe that the life path of his life partner, beloved wife, and loyal companion Zarifa Saidnosirova is truly an example for all our sisters. This is because Zarifa, who was a true source of support for Oybek, was a shining star in loyalty, devotion, and wisdom. [2]

Today, a variety of spiritual-educational and artistic-literary events are being held in our country. In many of these events, the focus is directly on the life and works of Oybek, and these topics are presented to the general public for deeper understanding.

Now, let me briefly introduce you to the life of Oybek, the great mentor.

The great writer was born on January 10, 1905, in the Gavkush neighborhood of Tashkent. During the Soviet era, before the spread of Russian ideology and the expulsion of their goods from the area, the majority of people living in this neighborhood were involved in silk production. Oybek's father, Toshmuhammad aka, initially worked in silk production and later traveled to villages, where he worked as a grocer. Born into a simple family, Oybek initially received his education at school. Although subjects like history, mathematics, and geography were not taught at this school, Oybek became acquainted with the lives of Uzbek and Persian-Tajik poets such as So'fi Olloyor, Navoiy, Khwaja Hafiz, and Bedil. In 1919, he continued his studies at the initial Soviet school called "Na'muna." Born in a modest and somewhat crooked house in a narrow alley, after completing his school in 1921, he moved to the dormitory of the Navoiy Pedagogical Technical School. Here, he met his future wife, Zarifa Saidnosirova, and became familiar with the works of such esteemed writers as Navoiy, Fuzuli, Pushkin, Lermontov, Tolstoy, and many other renowned authors. [3]

From those early years, Oybek became interested in writing and was inspired to create his first poem, which was published in the technical school's wall newspaper, *Tong Yulduzi* (Morning Star). According to him, after his poem was published, he was appointed as the responsible editor of the newspaper. Slowly, his poems began to be published in the *Respublika* newspaper. Oybek himself humorously recalled and emphasized these times many years later. In 1925, after finishing his studies, he enrolled in the Faculty of Economics at the Central Asian State University while also teaching language and literature at a school.

The great writer Oybek has left behind a rich creative legacy with several famous works, including *Qutluq Qon* (The Sacred Blood), *Navoiy, Sayyohi Hindi* (The Indian Traveler), *Quyosh Qoraymas* (The Sun Never Darkens), *Oltin Vodiydan Shabadalar* (Winds from the Golden Valley), *Ulug' Yo'l* (The Great Path), *Bolalik Xotiralarim* (My Childhood Memories), and many others, which occupy significant places in both world and Uzbek literature.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that in today's world, rich in changes, each of us must strive to become individuals who can contribute meaningfully to the development of our country with advanced knowledge and wisdom. On this path, by following the exemplary life journeys and rich literary heritage of great individuals, we will undoubtedly take steps towards perfection.

We believe that the article above will encourage all young people to reflect, read books, and increase the number of those who study the creative works of our beloved mentor, the great writer Oybek.

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